

Design Technology Co-Optimization Method for RF EDA

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I. Introduction

II. QPZD nonlinear model

III. Statistical model and yield optimization

IV. MMIC IP model

V. Conculsion

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I. Introduction

Semiconductor Technology Landscape:

I. Introduction

Design Technology Co-Optimization

[Lu, IEDM 2018 Tutorial]

Multi-physics coupling

- Another option beyond technology scaling
- Early feedback in process development

I. Introduction

DTCO for RF circuits require **Cross-layer Physical Models(CPM)**

- Connection the device parameters to electrical parameters
- Conduct the device parameters design for higher electrical performance

I. Introduction

DTCO for RF circuits: From material to system

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II. QPZD transistor model

History of compact models

Advanced/4th : ACM、EKV (EPFL) 、BSIM5/6、MOS11、PSP (NXP) 、HiSIM (Hiroshima)

II. QPZD transistor model

II. QPZD transistor model

Concept of compact models

Intrinsic Models

- Ideal device model
- Real device model

II. QPZD transistor model

Motivation of Quasi-Physical Zone Division model

GaN ASM-HEMT Model

GaN MVSG Model

- Many fitting parameters for real devices
- Convergency

GaN QPZD Model

Models	Approx. Number of Parameters	Self-Heating Effects	Trapping Effects	Ambient Temperature Effects
Modified Angelov [4]	53	✓	✓	--
Angelov GaN [8]	35	✓	✓	--
Modified Angelov [30]	35	✓	✓	--
Surface Potential [16]	30	✓	✓	--
Surface Potential [18]	29	✓	✓	--
Zone Division [22]	5	--	--	--
This Work (QPZD)	24	✓	✓	✓

- Simplify functions
- Reserve physical parameters

II. QPZD transistor model

Core IV Model

Zone division theory

Parameter extraction flowchart

$$I_{ds} = \frac{I_{max} V_{ds} (1 + \lambda V_{ds})}{\sqrt{\beta E_c^\beta (l_s + l_d)^\beta + (E_c l_g + V_{ds})^\beta}}$$

Electron sheet density model

$$n_s = A_n \cdot \tanh(\alpha_n \cdot (V_{gs} - V_{off}) + b_n) + B_n$$

Critical electric field model

$$E_c = (a_0 + a_1 V_{gs}) (b_0 + b_1 T_{ch} + b_2 T_{ch}^2)$$

Threshold voltage model

$$V_{off}(T) = \phi_B(T) - \Delta E_c(T) - \frac{qN_d d_d^2}{2\epsilon_{AlGaN}} - \frac{q\sigma(d_d + d_i)}{\epsilon_{AlGaN}}$$

II. QPZD transistor model

Parasitic EM model

Device Structure

$$Y_{11} = j\omega(C_{gsx} + C_{gdx})$$

$$Y_{22} = j\omega(C_{dsx} + C_{gdx})$$

$$Y_{12} = Y_{21} = j\omega C_{gdx}$$

Parameter extraction flowchart

II. QPZD transistor model

Thermal model

Self-heating Effects

$$T_{ch} = T_0 + P_{diss} R_{th}$$

$$R_{th} = R_{th_GaN} + R_{th_Sub} + R_{th_Die-attach}$$

Parameter	Meaning
Lg	Gate length
tsub	Substrate thickness
tGaN	buffer thickness
Wg	Gate width
...	...

Buffer:

$$\Delta T_{GaN} = \frac{P_{diss}}{\pi N W_g K_{GaN}} \ln\left(\frac{4t_{GaN}}{\pi Lg}\right)$$

Substrate:

$$\Delta T_{Sub_up1} = \frac{P_{diss}}{\pi N W_g K_{Sub}} \ln\left(\frac{\eta s^2}{t_{GaN} W_g}\right)$$

Die attach:

$$\Delta T_{Die_attach} = \frac{P_{diss} t_{Die_attach}}{K_{Die_attach} A_{Die_attach}}$$

II. QPZD transistor model

Trapping model

SRH model for trapping

Equivalent circuit model

① Electron capture

② Electron emission

③ Hole capture

④ Hole emission

} Electron Trap

$$\frac{dp_D}{dt} = c_n N_C \left[(N_D - p_D) e^{\frac{E_D - E_C}{kT/q}} - p_D e^{\frac{E_F - E_C}{kT/q}} \right]$$

Emission: $i_E = \omega_o C_T (V_0 - v_T)$

Capture: $i_C = \omega_o C_T v_T \exp\left(\frac{v_I}{kT/q}\right)$

II. QPZD transistor model

Noise Model

Equivalent circuit model

Model	Fitting Parameter Number
Pucel	3
Pospieszalski	2
ASM-HEMT	3
MVSG	3
This model	0

Channel thermal noise

$$S_{I_g} = 4kT_{ch} \omega^2 W^2 C_g^2 \left(\frac{W^4 \mu^4 C_g^4 A_{ig}^2}{I_d^5 L^2} A_{id} - \frac{2W^3 \mu^3 C_g^3 A_{ig}}{I_d^4 L} B_{ig} + \dots \right)$$

Gate-induced noise

$$S_{I_d} = \frac{4kT_{ch} W^2 C_g^2 \mu_{eff}^2}{L^2 I_{ds}} \left[(V_L - V_{si}) V_{go}^2 - (V_L^2 - V_{si}^2) V_{go} + \frac{1}{3} (V_L^3 - V_{si}^3) \right]$$

Noise correlation

$$C = \frac{S_{I_g} I_d}{\sqrt{S_{I_g} S_{I_d}}} = \frac{-j \left(A_{ig} A_{id} - \frac{I_d L}{W \mu C_g} B_{ig} \right)}{\sqrt{A_{id} \left(A_{ig}^2 A_{id} - \frac{2I_d L}{C_g \mu W} A_{ig} B_{ig} + \frac{I_d^2 L^2}{C_g^2 \mu^2 W^2} C_{ig} \right)}}$$

II. QPZD transistor model

Model Validation

Pulse-IV

Fundamental RF performance

Noise

Harmonic RF performance

S parameter

Linearity performance

II. QPZD transistor model

Device Co-optimization

Technical Parameter Analysis

Barrier thickness

Al mole fraction

Thermal Management

MSL structure

ISV structure

Channel temperature

II. QPZD transistor model

Device Co-optimization for MMIC

In house parameters extraction

PDK for EDA tools

GaN MMIC optimization

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III. Statistical model and yield optimization

Statistical model

Process fluctuation

Output variation

Low yield circuit design in some cases

Golden Die

- Data-based
- Poor extrapolation

For circuit evaluation

TCAD Model

- Fully physical
- Time expensive

For device optimization

Physical-based Model

- Physically interpretable
- Fast simulation

Co-optimization

III. Statistical model and yield optimization

QPZD Statistical Model

Parameter extraction flowchart

$$\tilde{X} = \mu_X + \sigma_X \left(\sum_{i=1}^3 L_{Xi} F_i + \varepsilon_X \right) \quad (X = d, v_{max}, \mu_{sat}, n_s)$$

Physical parameters variation modeling

$$I_{ds} = f_1(d, v_{max}, \mu_{sat}, n_{smax}) = \frac{I_{max} V_{ds} (1 + \lambda V_{ds})}{\sqrt{\beta} E_{ceff}^\beta (l_s + l_d)^\beta + (E_{ceff} l_g + V_{ds})^\beta}$$

QPZD nonlinear model

Characterization of the fluctuation

III. Statistical model and yield optimization

GaN MMIC Yield Optimization

Traditional Method

New Method

III. Statistical model and yield optimization

GaN MMIC Yield Optimization

Yield load-pull flowchart

Boundary setting

Optimum impedance considering yield and output performance

III. Statistical model and yield optimization

GaN MMIC Yield Optimization

32~38GHz 15W GaN PA

Boundary	Values	
P _{outmin}	43dBm	42dBm
Gainmin	16dB	
Gainmax	18dB	
PAE _{min}	31%	30%
Yield	81.3%	98.2%

Optimum impedance selection

P_{out}

13% improvement comparing with conventional method

Comparison with conventional method

PAE

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IV. Circuit IP model

GaN MMIC IP model

MMIC IP model for EDA tools

Junction temperatures Vs. Pin & RF frequency

Performance

IV. Circuit IP model

Electro-thermal Analysis of GaN MMIC

Thermal analysis of PA with package

IV. Circuit IP model

Electro-thermal(Eth) Analysis of GaN MMIC

2~6 GHz 10W GaN PA

Thermal distribution
(Mo-Cu heat sink)

Thermal distribution
(QFN package)

Pout Vs. ambient temperatures

Pout Vs. packages

IV. Circuit IP model

Electro-thermal Analysis of GaN MMIC

2~6 GHz GaN LNA

Thermal distribution
(Mo-Cu heat sink)

Thermal distribution
(QFN package)

NF Vs. temperatures

NF Vs. packages

IV. Circuit IP model

Electro-thermal Analysis of GaN T/R MMIC

Power Amplifier

Low-noise Amplifier

Switch

T - transmitter

RF output (T)

S parameter (T)

R - Receiver

Noise Figure (R)

S parameter (R)

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V. Conclusion

- The design technology co-optimization (**DTCO**) for **RF EDA** is introduced taking **GaN MMIC** for example.
- The **physics-based nonlinear transistor model** can realize a good mapping between physical parameters and circuit electrical performance.
- The **statistical model** can realize a good mapping between process variation and circuit yield.
- The **DTCO** and **STCO** will be useful for next generation of RF design.

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**Thank you for your
attention!**